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Innovative technology in Teaching Russian as a Foreign Language: Flipped Learning Approach

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Abstract

The article raises an important topic of the effectiveness of using e-learning tools in optimizing the process of teaching Russian language to Korean students. The organizer of the educational process is faced with the task of selecting the most progressive ways to achieve specific goals: to introduce students to speech context and Russian-speaking environment of cultural and everyday communication; to prevent language interference caused by the mother tongue. Purpose of the study is based on ethno-methodological educational content; the proposed methodology is associated with traditional teaching methods that have been used for a long time in Korea. The study analyzed theoretical and practical discussions of the flipped learning paradigm from previous studies through using a descriptive method of research and method of philosophical analysis.

Our proposed methodology has been tested at two South Korean universities (Incheon National University and Dankook University). About 70 students took part in the scientific and practical experiment. Flipped Learning Approach is expected to be effective for students in other countries as well. The idea of the Flipped learning approach becomes the model that helps to organize the educational process taking into account the individual characteristics of each student.

Finally, the innovative technologies in education are necessary tools for the formation of the linguistic culture of the individual. The Flipped Learning approach provides great opportunities for deepening the creative potential of students, expanding their individual capabilities, and developing critical thinking skills that are necessary to form the corresponding competencies of students.

Keywords: innovative technologies, foreign language teaching, ethno-methodological aspect, Flipped Learning approach.

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Introduction

Following new trends in the development of science and education, linguists and methodologists were tasked with improving methodological recommendations in the field of teaching a foreign language, relying on the student's cultural background. Thus, this is helping a student to properly adapt to a foreign language and its cultural environment, without going beyond the usual learning conditions. Mostly instructors of foreign languages in Korea, especially Russian as Foreign Language Courses have common difficulties such as lack of exposure, insufficient time for class, practice, activities, and level difference of Korean learners (Han, 2018).

However, the ways to overcome problems have not been researched properly. This article suggests applying a flipped learning Korean language classroom for Russian education. According to previous studies, applying the way of study is effective in enhancing self-directed learning, encouraging an in-depth study of foreign language, and stimulating interaction between two sides of the educational process: between the learner and the teacher. The author sets his task to compare Asian educational traditions with the proposed method of teaching a foreign language as the Flipped Learning Approach. Additionally, this article implies that it would be possible to reduce the level gap between the learners and to use class time more efficiently.

Over the past decade, flipping the classroom is a new concept that has entered the pedagogical world and has become a new phenomenon. This phenomenon was popularized by high-profile publications in *The New York Times* and *The Chronicle of Higher Education and Science* (Brame, 2013). Many articles have been written about this phenomenon, the new educational paradigm, most commonly known as inverted education (Bergmann & Sams, 2012). This term was used to refer to any type of Internet technology for working in the classroom.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the method was to free the teacher from the learning process and to shift his attention to the needs of students. In the format created by the teacher, the students had to study video materials at home. The very principle of the inverted classroom model is that while the students study the new material during homework, they repeat and discuss it in the classroom. According to many scholars, academic performance has been enhanced by this form of work. Grades and answers or adjustments individually for each student in the class contribute to a better understanding of course matters (Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

Students had more responsibility and commitment, more dynamically and the outcomes can be increased along with self-efficacy (Namik, Boae, & Im, 2014). Doing assignments in the classroom gives teachers a better understanding of the difficulties and learning styles of students (Fulton, 2012). These ideas were promising and attracted a huge number of researchers and educators. Methods and ways of teaching: question and answer, demonstrations, simulations, peer tutoring, feedback, and role-playing. This reflective and active learning approach can enhance and support undergraduate learning through collaborative group work and increased interaction between students and lecturers (Nahar & Chowdhury, 2019).

Literature review

To date, a large database of relatively new trends in the development of education, linguistics, teaching methods of Russian as a foreign language has been accumulated. These studies are reflected in the works of Antonova and Merenkov (2018), Ahmed (2016), Basalgina (2014), Tikhonova (2018), Han (2018), Fulton, (2012), Crouch and Mazur (2001), Bergmann and Sams (2012), Auvinen, Hakulinen, and Malmi (2015), Asanova (2019), Alsowat (2016), Levy (2010) and others.

Based on the research of the above listed works, we tried to take a look at the problem of using the inverted classroom methodology, together with the ethno-methodical approach inherent in the Korean educational system and to compare all the positive and negative aspects of using the inverted classroom methodology in Korea.

What is the Flipped Learning Approach? The definition says that Flipped learning is a pedagogical approach in which the conventional notion of classroom-based learning is inverted, so that students are introduced to the learning material before class, with classroom time then being used to deepen understanding through discussion with peers and problem-solving activities facilitated.

From Figure 1, we can make a conclusion that a flipped classroom pedagogical approach can be a good alternative to the traditional classroom way of teaching. As research showed this methodical approach was adopted in many educational societies because this way can deliver prospects for improving peer interaction and deeply engage with learning materials.

Dynamic learning techniques using the flipped approach get many benefits in which learners have to involve in meaningful educational activities and reflect on what they are doing (Prince, 2004). A few types of learning activities were enumerated as commonly used, for instance, digital textbooks, and videos, online study materials through websites or learning desk, virtual labs, and game-based learning.

Figure 1. Traditional Classroom and Flipped Classroom

There are many positive reviews for using video with distance learning students, who could master their skills by watching them repeatedly. The virtual lab and lingua-simulators helped to solve many practical problems by improving grammar and lexical skills. The game-based learning gave students the potential power and enthusiasm to study continuously. Students faced a lot of challenges, to be well prepared for the class was not such a simple task, but this approach we can name as the students-centered approach of the flipped classroom.

This method was introduced in the early mid-2000s by chemistry teachers Jon Bergman and Aaron Sams, and the founder of online Khan Academy Salman Khan. And earlier in the 1990s, one of Harvard Professor Eric Mazur developed a model of 'peer instruction' in which he provided material for students to prepare and reflect on before class and then used class time to encourage deeper cognitive thinking via peer interaction and instructor challenges. He called this "just in time teaching" (Crouch & Mazur, 2001).

Methodology

In our research, we compared this method with the traditional method of Korean educational way. Given the need for innovative teaching tools, special attention should be paid to the ethnic characteristics of a student studying a foreign language. An effective means of increasing the effectiveness of the process of mastering the language is to take into account the ethno-cultural and ethno-psychological characteristics of students.

What training conditions are inherent in his native country; what forms of education the student is adapted to in pre-university education. A deep analysis and synthesis of student's ethno-psychology in combination with innovative teaching methods increase the effectiveness of the learning process. Experimental work was conducted among students studying the following disciplines "Russian for beginners", "Basic Russian course", "Advanced Russian reading and writing", over two years.

During the first semester of study, the traditional methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language was used. The author used a technique familiar to the Russian teaching system. The emphasis on the ethno-cultural side of education was introduced gradually; the reason was one important circumstance. Students involved in different subjects had different levels of Russian language proficiency, which greatly complicated the work of the teacher. The author made an attempt to find a compromise method for solving the problem, which takes place less often in Russian universities because groups of students are formed by the level of language proficiency. In Korean universities, there is another practice of choosing a subject for study; it is based on the individual curriculum of each student.

In order to maintain the motivation of Asian students, it is very important to be based on the strengths of ethno-psychology: a high level of mental abilities (memorization, tabular presentation of the contents of the lesson (especially grammar should be introduced in the form of tables)); visual channel of perception and visual-motor type of memory, the use of analogies and contextual guesses. Moreover, students' desire to "save face", they have the priority of the family over the individual, the tendency to monotonous work, to be refined, detailed. But the most important aspect is the relevance of the Confucian principles to self-improvement and self-education, students who are studying a foreign language must combine collective forms of work and independent ones. It should be noted that the form of control should be more like an analysis than criticism.

The traditional way of Korean educational method has three steps of the introduction of learning content: - Preview- before the lesson (the classical form of school education), when students independently study the content of the lesson at home, because during the lesson, it is not customary allowed to ask questions to the teacher so as not to demonstrate poor preparedness for the lesson; - During the lesson, all students listen to teacher's presentation and practice working through it; - After school to do review the content of the lesson again while doing homework.

Working with the usual European system of presenting new learning materials, we want to note that we had lower indicators of progress. Exploring the traditional forms of Korean education, we came to the conclusion that the ethno-oriented method of the lesson gives a deeper teaching effect. The effectiveness

rate grows to 30%. The calculation was very obvious; beginner-level students (A1) were divided into two groups. Within a month, one group received training content in advance, and another one – in the traditional European style.

After one month, the students had a test, which was conducted on the competence of lexical and grammatical materials, passed during this time. The second group of students demonstrated their knowledge 30% higher than the first group. A similar experiment was conducted several times with students of different levels of language proficiency. The result of the experiment was identical. The conclusion suggests itself; the traditional technique is inferior to the Flipped classroom approach 3) at the control stage of the experiment, there was identified the dynamics of changes in the levels of the three components of readiness for family life of the subjects in the EG and the CG, and there was tested the effectiveness of the developed pedagogical conditions. The SPSS statistical package, version 23.0, was used to process the results of the study.

Figure 2. Testing chat

For comparison with Flipped Learning:

Students learn new content at their own pace at home. Then, in class, the teacher facilitates student-led discussions and learning activities that allow students to develop their understanding. The teachers who use Flipped learning can deeply encourage students' thinking. They also can be true facilitators of learning. Additionally, teachers are far more than a "textbook". The actual purpose of this research is to design a

flipped Russian teaching and learning method to solve the big issue for non-language environment in foreign countries, and to find out the effectiveness of applying the flipped learning approach through qualitative and quantitative studies. This method has some pros and cons.

The Pros: 1) Students have more control- the freedom to study in their own way; time to review material without getting left behind; 2) It supports student-centered learning environment and collaboration – gives the opportunity to teach and learn from each other, and partake in their own learning; 3) Easier access to lessons and content – video lectures are available at all times; 4) Parents can easier track their kid's progress rate- parents can help their students; 5) It can be more productive – more time for personal things to do, and academic practice; 6) The interest in group work in the classroom is increasing; students help each other, critically evaluate each other's achievements; 7) The individual characteristics of each student are taken into account; more time is given to those students who need additional support and help; 8) This technology contributes to a more productive use of time - more time is devoted to academic practice, more free time for personal affairs; 9) There is an opportunity for computer diagnostics, testing the quality of students' knowledge.

The Cons: 1) It can create or exacerbate a digital divide –access to Internet and computer (additional fees); 2) It relies on preparation and trust – there is no guarantee students will cooperate with the flipped model; 3) There is a big amount of work on the front-end – a lot of additional work for teacher; 4) Not naturally a test-prep form of learning – the flipped learning cannot teach test preparation content; 5) Some students with great difficulty getting used to the new teaching technology, to a large initial load; 6) The orientation of students to compulsory homework, which is extremely difficult for some students; 7) Significantly increases the student's time in front of the computer, which may indirectly affect his health (Acedo, 2020).

Results

After examining all pros and cons, the flipped learning approach still has very effective results compared with traditional ways of education. The effectiveness of using computer technology to learn a foreign language is beyond doubt. In the late 90s, Michael Levy tried to establish (CALL) in disciplinary and historical contexts, because until that time the development and study of language using a computer were not systematized. In his work, he gave an in-depth review (CALL). It is necessary to explain what (CALL) is Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) (Levy, 1997).

In his work, he relied on a survey in eighteen countries. He examined the relationship between theoretical knowledge and the practical application of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL), developed the

conceptual and practical roles of a teacher using computer tools. He also discussed the serious importance of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) for computer programming. He examined the usefulness and uniqueness of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) for learning and teaching foreign languages. Levy's study reflected the multifaceted aspects that are reflected in constantly evolving technologies that teachers and students will like for their practicality in applied linguistics. He shows this to be of value for a better understanding of methodology, integration of CALL into the curriculum, the role of the teacher and learner, and evaluation. Later, his idea merged and a new educational paradigm arose, like the Flipped Learning Approach.

Discussions

The Flipped classroom learners can better remember, understand, and apply their knowledge, analyze learned things, evaluate the content of the lesson, and finally create a better idea. So, they access higher-order thinking, engage more in the content, enjoy the learning process, and learn more efficiently. Flipped learning changes the role of the teacher from an instruction giver, to a true facilitator of learning. This student-centered approach of the Flipped classroom gives flexibility and potential for developing and applying the critical thinking skills that are needed to get a major education.

Ten years ago, Levy wrote that students will use wireless devices everywhere and will become an integral part of the learning process. Currently, Internet technology has advanced significantly. "Cloud computing and services such as YouTube, Teacher Tube, and Screencast.com make video sharing more accessible for all teachers and students. Technology educators predict that tablet PCs, laptops, or smartphones with wireless access in a few years almost all students will wear the Internet" (Levy, 2010, p.77). Today it has become a reality.

Modern technologies allow us to change the entire content of the lesson, due to multimedia. Learning is becoming more fun and interesting, and it means more motivating. A regular review of the effectiveness of the Flipped classroom model in distance learning is timely, as this blended approach has obtained popularity among teachers. A review of the articles contained in this study was composed around three questions about a flipped classroom model.

Conclusion

The conclusion of this study demonstrates a growing trend of research using this model in various areas of traditional classroom education; by the way, just a few studies have been dedicated to this methodology of applying in distance learning. This demonstrates the lack of research in practical work experience that can

be achieved through the introduction of new technologies, such as video recordings, home design projects, and webcasts of language-laboratory classes.

Popular educational and documentary films, various video instructions and video lectures, video recordings of studies and training, dubbed presentations and other media are actively used as educational materials. It is essential that the applying of these training tools to achieve their objectives would provide the necessary information in high quality and accessible to all technical devices.

If there is a need to attach training exercises to the video, organize a survey, discussion, provide the video with additional information or links to web resources, then the video becomes interactive. Interactive video solves a number of problems: it facilitates viewing of educational material: it gives tips, comments along the way, and with the help of links to other web resources, it expands the informational resources: activates and controls the assimilation of new material (assignments, tests, quizzes, discussions); introduces an element of the game, makes it possible to select a plot when watching a video.

In addition to preparing a training video, for the teacher, it is important to organize the availability of tools for self-control. Such tools can be interactive didactic tasks and games (for example, created in the services Learningapps.org, Kahoot.it, and Kuizizz.com), interactive tests (a service for creating tests Master-test.net). These interactive services are also innovative assessment tools. The lesson preparing process can be accompanied by special tasks-templates which help to comprehend new information. In this case, you can use specially prepared templates in a tabular form, which contain specific questions and assignments for educational material (text documents in a Google form).

Now the inverted training with direct upload to YouTube is available in iSpring Suite. To control the progress of students in the process of preparing for classes, special tables are used that record the success of students, allow you to make notes along the way, which ensures the competitive nature of training. An important function can be performed by diaries, which make it possible to identify and record all kinds of difficulties in the learning process, focus on emerging issues, and capture students' thoughts on individual problems. It becomes obvious that the educational system will strive for personalization. The inverted class becomes a model that helps to organize the learning process with a personal approach.

The following service platforms can be used to implement the Inverted Class model: Lore is a stream of courses where teachers compose lectures from pictures, presentations, tables, audio and video clips. Eliademy is the educational platform of the Finnish company CBTEC, which was founded by Nokia employees. Eliademy places the course in a browser - you can even see Excel spreadsheets and PowerPoint presentations right on the spot. Teachers leave voice notes under the uploaded files - this is how Eliademy

forms lectures. Each lesson can be associated with specific homework. EduBrite is a web service where you can add the necessary files, and then the author places them in the correct order and writes comments on each of the files. After creating a few lessons, they can be linked into a course and completed with a test on the material passed.

Moodle is a course management system from Australia. Immediately after registration, the platform determines the technical issues - privacy settings, indicating the duration of the course, etc. You can collect lectures from different files and prepare the final exam. It is possible to insert the course as a module into other sites using special program code. Moodle also has the opportunity to do surveys, glossaries, profiles and small databases.

Versal is a platform on which each course is created from functional elements - videos, diagrams, pictures, explanatory notes, etc. Elements are created by adding icons to the workspace, where you can arrange them in the correct order. Upon completion, Versal provides a link to the course, which you can send to your students or post on social networks.

Thus, the technology of the Flipped classroom helps to enrich the educational process, to form modern key competencies among students: to set and successfully solve cognitive tasks; to educate students in research skills; to form competencies of information technologies; competencies of social interaction in a team, skills in a group; to cultivate the ability to listen and respect fellow students, distribute responsibilities, help teammates.

The effectiveness of the technology of the “inverted class” is expressed in the solution of a number of important tasks: creating free communication, manifesting the initiative and activity of students, their independence in the choice of methods of activity; providing conditions for independent, creative understanding of the topic under study; assistance in the analysis and evaluation of new knowledge. As noted by Tikhonova (2018) the advantage of this model lies in changing the structure of the key components of the educational process. The traditional sequence of competencies involved is changing: memorization, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis, evaluation (Tikhonova, 2018).

The usage of electronic services in the classes for the study Russian as a foreign language with Korean students makes them not passive observers, but active participants in the educational process increase the students' interest in learning the Russian language, helps them to work creatively, and gains knowledge independently. This study allows us to conclude that innovative technologies in education are an essential tool of identity formation. They open up new possibilities for creating a personalized professionally-oriented mobile space that meets the modern competently-oriented concept of education. The emphasis is on teaching the ability to independently find the necessary information, identify

problems and find solutions, critically analyze the knowledge gained and apply it effectively in practice.

Having instant access to authentic resources, educational materials and programs, the participants of the educational process are able to perform tasks, communicate with each other at any time and in any place. The Flipped Learning approach provides great opportunities for deepening the creative potential of students, expanding their individual capabilities, and developing the critical thinking skills that are necessary to form the corresponding competencies of professionally oriented students. The present research is dedicated to positive change in education, as it gives a researched-based deep educational foundation of flipped learning drawn from the groundwork of literature on the Flipped Learning Approach.

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